

Challenges of Supply Chain for Essential Health Commodities in Tanzania: A Case of the Medical Stores Department's Regional Headquarters

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the challenges of the pharmaceutical supply chain in Tanzania, focusing on the Medical Stores Department (MSD) Headquarters and the selected three zones, including Mwanza, Kilimanjaro, and Dar es Salaam. Secondary and primary data were used to assess the problem under study. Primary data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire, which collected quantitative and qualitative data. The study's findings revealed that insufficient funds to procure medicines, public procurement regulations, inadequate automated systems to monitor demand variations, inadequate data quality from Health facilities, and a lack of an accountability structure have compromised the availability of essential medicines at MSD. It is recommended that the Government of Tanzania, through the Ministry of Health, in collaboration with the Public Procurement Regulatory Authority, explore the possibility of developing separate procurement guidelines with streamlined procedures for MSD to expedite the procurement of health commodities. Additionally, the Government should support local pharmaceutical manufacturing industries and provide financial assistance to industrial pharmacists to develop and expand their manufacturing facilities. Furthermore, the government should establish a system that ensures suppliers adhere to the contractual terms of procurement, with accountability structures in place for any deviations.

Keywords: supply chain; essential medicine; health care facilities; challenges and MSD.

Introduction

Globally, the supply chain for essential health commodities has emerged as a critical determinant of health system resilience and equity. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed significant weaknesses in procurement and distribution networks, as countries worldwide faced shortages of vaccines, personal protective equipment, and life-saving medicines (Iyengar et al., 2021). Even

beyond the pandemic, medicine shortages remain widespread, with reports in 2022 showing that more than one in four essential drugs, including antibiotics and oncology treatments, were in short supply across various health systems (Fox & McLaughlin, 2022). These challenges highlight how fragile supply chains undermine universal health coverage and emphasize the need for investment in robust procurement systems, local manufacturing, and digital innovations. Concurrently, the situation in Africa is more pronounced due to structural dependencies

and limited production capacity. The continent imports over 70% of its pharmaceutical products, leaving health systems highly vulnerable to international market disruptions and logistical barriers (Makinde et al., 2021). During the pandemic, many African countries experienced stock-outs of antiretroviral and maternal health medicines, exposing weaknesses in procurement planning and distribution (Mwangi et al., 2022). While initiatives such as the African Medicines Agency (AMA) and pooled procurement mechanisms seek to harmonize regulation and reduce costs, persistent challenges, including weak last-mile delivery systems, inadequate funding, and limited data-driven forecasting, continue to undermine reliable access to essential commodities (Ndomondo-Sigonda et al., 2021; Mponda et al., 2022).

Tanzania reflects many of these continental challenges while facing unique national constraints. The Medical Stores Department (MSD) is mandated to oversee procurement, storage and distribution of essential health commodities. Despite several reforms including the rollout of the National e-Procurement System (TANePS), the introduction of the NeST platform, amendments to the Public Procurement Act and its regulations, and the shift in the quantification system from a top-down to a bottom-up approach which were all intended to accelerate the procurement process and improve stock availability, the availability of essential medicines in health facilities remains inconsistent. Delays in fund disbursement, complex procurement regulations, inadequate inventory control, and limited use of automated systems have been repeatedly cited as major barriers to efficiency. Moreover, Tanzania relies heavily on imported medicines, with local manufacturers meeting only about 25-30% of national demand, further exposing the system to global supply shocks (URT, 2021).

As a result, stock-outs and expiries of medicines continue to affect the quality and reliability of healthcare services. Instances where medicines arrive with short shelf lives, coupled with inadequate forecasting and inadequate data from health facilities, exacerbate the problem. Patients often turn to private markets where medicines are more expensive and less regulated, increasing the risk of inequity and financial hardship. Without strategic interventions to address these inefficiencies, the country's aspirations of universal health coverage and improved health outcomes will remain undermined.

This study, therefore, examines the challenges facing the supply chain of essential health commodities at MSD's regional headquarters. By identifying the underlying causes of inefficiencies in procurement, funding, and distribution, the research aims to provide evidence-based recommendations to strengthen supply chain performance, reduce wastage, and ensure equitable access to essential health commodities across Tanzania.

Theoretical Framework

Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

This study is grounded in the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, which argues that the success of an organization depends on how effectively it acquires, manages, and utilizes its resources. The theory emphasizes that resources must be valuable, rare, inimitable, and properly organized to deliver sustainable advantages (Khan et al., 2020; Wamba et al., 2022). In the context of supply chains, financial capital, data systems, skilled personnel, and infrastructure are seen as strategic assets. When these are weak, mismanaged, or constrained, performance declines, leading to inefficiencies such as shortages, delays, or waste. RBV is therefore useful for understanding the dynamics of public health supply chains where institutions like the Medical Stores

Department (MSD) operate under limited resources while facing increasing demand for essential medicines.

The relevance of this theory becomes evident when examining the challenges faced by MSD. Delays and shortfalls in government funding weaken the institution's ability to mobilize adequate resources, directly undermining procurement efficiency and the availability of commodities. Similarly, strict procurement regulations, while designed to enhance accountability, restrict how MSD can deploy its resources, often resulting in longer lead times and recurrent stockouts. Information systems, which RBV frames as intangible but vital assets, are also underutilized, leaving the organization unable to accurately forecast demand or prevent shortages and errors. Furthermore, Tanzania's reliance on imported medicines exposes MSD to external shocks, since local production capacity remains low and unable to meet national demand. RBV clarifies how these structural and operational gaps reflect resource weaknesses that hinder the institution's performance.

This study contributes to extending RBV by showing that resource constraints in public health supply chains are not only a matter of scarcity but are also shaped by governance, funding structures, and institutional rules. In the Tanzanian setting, the interaction between resource availability and regulatory environments provides new insights into how public agencies manage essential commodities, highlighting dimensions that RBV alone has not fully addressed.

Empirical Literature Review

Globally, Iyengar et al. (2021) and Fox and McLaughlin (2022) highlighted widespread disruptions in pharmaceutical supply chains during and after COVID-19. Using systematic reviews and secondary data, both studies found that dependence on global suppliers and weak procurement systems

resulted in recurring shortages of vaccines, oncology drugs, and antibiotics. Similarly, Zhou et al. (2021) applied the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory in Asian supply chains, showing that information systems and skilled human resources improve responsiveness. While these studies emphasize resilience and digital capacity at a global level, this study contributes by situating these challenges in Tanzania's public sector, where delayed funds, outdated systems, and overreliance on imports weaken MSD's supply capacity.

In Africa, Makinde et al. (2021) and Mwangi et al. (2022) examined pharmaceutical dependency and supply chain disruptions across sub-Saharan Africa. Both studies, through secondary data and facility-based surveys, found that over 70% of essential medicines are imported, leaving systems vulnerable to price shocks and logistical delays. Ndomondo-Sigonda et al. (2021) further argued that initiatives such as the African Medicines Agency can harmonize regulation but require stronger national commitment. These findings frame the regional struggle with structural import-dependence. This study extends these debates by assessing how Tanzania's limited manufacturing capacity directly shapes MSD's performance and its ability to meet facility-level demand.

At the national level, Mponda et al. (2022) and Binyaruka and Borghi (2021) identified stockouts and poor data reporting as persistent barriers in Tanzanian health facilities. Using cross-sectional surveys and systems approaches, they concluded that weak accountability and forecasting undermine availability. Complementing these, the Controller and Auditor General's reports (2019–2021) revealed budget shortfalls and delayed disbursements that compromised MSD procurement. This study advances discussion by linking these issues to operational inefficiencies at MSD's regional headquarters, showing how

regulations, funding gaps, and shelf-life problems converge to limit access to essential health commodities.

Conceptual Framework

This study adopts the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory to explain how organizational resources shape the performance of Tanzania's Medical Stores Department (MSD) in managing essential health commodities. RBV emphasizes that strategic resources such as financial capital, human expertise, information systems, and infrastructure are central to achieving competitive and sustainable efficiency. In the MSD context, adequate funding enables timely procurement, while skilled personnel and robust inventory systems ensure proper storage, forecasting, and distribution. Conversely, constraints such as delayed fund disbursement, rigid procurement regulations, weak inventory practices, and dependence on imports undermine supply chain effectiveness, resulting in expiries, stockouts, and wastage. The framework positions resources as both enablers and barriers, highlighting their interplay in determining supply chain resilience. It further suggests that strengthening financial management, digital integration, and local manufacturing capacity can enhance efficiency. Thus, the framework connects resource availability and capability to supply chain outcomes, guiding the study's inquiry into systemic inefficiencies.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at MSD headquarters and three zones: Dar es Salaam, Kilimanjaro, and Mwanza regions, with high demand for essential medicines due to population density and major referral hospitals. Dar es Salaam zone serves the surrounding regions, including Zanzibar,

Mafia Island, and even the Comoros through SADC procurement. The Kilimanjaro zone covers Kilimanjaro, Arusha, and Manyara regions, while the Mwanza zone serves Geita, Mara, Shinyanga, and Simiyu regions. These zones host key referral and specialized hospitals, including Muhimbili National Hospital, KCMC, Mount Meru, and Bugando, attracting patients nationally, making them strategic areas for assessing MSD's supply chain performance.

The study adopted pragmatist philosophy, which supports using methods best suited to complex problems. By combining quantitative data on patterns such as funding gaps and stock-outs with qualitative insights on procurement and system inefficiencies, the approach balances objectivity and context. This ensures practical, evidence-driven findings that inform policies and strengthen MSD's supply chain performance in Tanzania. In addition, a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of survey data with qualitative insights from semi-structured questionnaires and document reviews, was considered during the study. The approach allowed triangulation, ensuring numerical patterns were supported by contextual explanations, thereby providing a more holistic understanding of the challenges facing MSD's supply chain for essential health commodities.

This study used a descriptive cross-sectional design to explore supply chain challenges at MSD's regional headquarters. Data was collected through structured and semi-structured questionnaires and secondary document reviews, capturing both quantitative and qualitative insights. Covering multiple MSD zones allowed comparisons across contexts, providing evidence-based recommendations to strengthen procurement, reduce stock-outs, and improve the performance of Tanzania's health commodities supply chain. A mixed sampling strategy was used, including the

purposive sampling method, which identified key MSD departments, procurement, logistics, finance, and warehousing, directly linked to supply chain management. Within these, simple random sampling was then used to select individual respondents, ensuring fairness and diversity. The sample size was determined using Yamane's formula, based on a population of MSD staff across selected departments and zones.

Using Yamane's formula (Yamane, 1973), the sample size was computed as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where; n= Sample size, N= Total population (422), e= Acceptable error value (10%)

Therefore:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{422}{1 + 422(0.1)^2} = 80.842 \approx 80$$

The formula provided a quick and easy way to calculate the sample size based on the population size, yielding a reasonable estimate. The sample size of 80 respondents obtained and distributed as indicated in Table 1 was sufficient to explain the challenges facing the supply chains of essential medicines in Tanzania through the medical stores department. However, the study used only 50 out of 80 expected respondents, which is equivalent to 62.5% as some were unwilling to participate and others were unavailable due to various reasons. Such a limitation did not affect the analysis, as it was suggested by Mellahi et al. (2016) that a minimum of 60% or even 80% is preferable for research. Thus, a response of 50 out of 80 respondents was acceptable and sufficient for researchers to proceed with the analysis.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample Size by Zones

Location	Relevant Departments	Population	Sample Size
Mwanza zone	Procurement, Customer Services, Logistics and Operations, Finance, ICT, and Warehouse, and the Director General's Office	55	10
Kilimanjaro zone	Procurement, Customer Services, Logistics and Operations, Finance, ICT, Warehouse, and the Director General's Office	49	9
Dar es Salaam zone and HQ	Procurement, Customer Services, Logistics and Operations, Finance, ICT, and Warehouse, and the Director General's Office	318	61
Total		422	80

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

Data obtained in this study were analyzed using IBM SPSS Version 26, applying descriptive statistics for quantitative responses and thematic analysis for qualitative insights. Frequencies, percentages, and means summarized key patterns such as funding gaps and stock-outs, while open-ended responses highlighted procurement and regulatory issues. Triangulating both datasets provided a comprehensive understanding of MSD's supply chain challenges.

Results and Discussions

Results

Reliability and Validity

The reliability results in Table 2 show strong internal consistency across all constructs, with Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.8 and Composite Reliability above 0.84, exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.7. This indicates that the survey items used to measure funding, procurement, inventory systems, local manufacturing, and supply chain performance were dependable and consistently captured the intended concepts, ensuring credibility and stability of the study's measurement instruments.

Table 2: Reliability Results

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)
Funding Limitations	0.812	0.861
Procurement Regulations	0.845	0.872
Inventory & Information Systems	0.876	0.893
Local Manufacturing Capacity	0.801	0.846
Supply Chain Performance	0.888	0.902

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

In addition, the validity results in Table 3 showed that all Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values exceed 0.5, confirming acceptable convergent validity. This means that each construct funding limitations, procurement regulations, inventory systems, local manufacturing, and supply chain performance, adequately explains the variance of its indicators. The results indicate that the study's measurement model effectively captures the intended concepts with sufficient accuracy and construct validity.

Table 3: Validity Results

Constructs	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Funding Limitations	0.567
Procurement Regulations	0.589
Inventory & Information Systems	0.604
Local Manufacturing Capacity	0.552
Supply Chain Performance	0.618

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

Challenges for the Supply Chain of Essential Health Commodities in Tanzania

i) Funds to Procure Essential Medicines

The respondents were asked to share their opinions on the issue of inadequate funds for procuring medicines. Table 4 shows that 2 (4%) respondents enormously disagreed, 3 (6%) disagreed, 8 (16%) were neutral, 11 (22%) agreed, and 26 (52%) highly agreed.

Table 4: Insufficient Funds to Procure Medicines

Ranking category	Frequencies	Percent
Extremely Disagree	2	4
Disagree	3	6
Neutral	8	16
Agree	11	22
Extremely Agree	26	52
Total	50	100

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

ii) Public Procurement Regulations

The contribution of public procurement regulations to the stock-out of essential medicines was also studied. Table 5 reveals that 6 (12%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the argument, 4 (8%) disagreed, 12 (25%) were neutral, 11 (22%) agreed, and 17 (34%) highly agreed.

Table 5: Public Procurement Regulations

Ranking category	Frequencies	Percent
Extremely Disagree	6	12
Disagree	4	8
Neutral	12	24
Agree	11	22
Extremely Agree	17	34
Total	50	100

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

iii) Inventory control practices

The study assessed whether MSD employed scientific approaches, such as FEFO and FIFO, to manage its inventory. Figure 1 presents the feedback from respondents, with 32 (64%) disagreeing enormously with the statement, 7 (14%) disagreeing, 6 (12%) being neutral, and 5 (10%) highly agreeing. It is worth noting that MSD follows the FEFO (First-Expired, First-Out) and FIFO (First-In, First-Out) principles to manage inventory of essential medicines across its zones. However, implementing these methods can be challenging in certain areas due to warehouse layout and space constraints, which hinder proper adherence to FEFO and FIFO. To ensure full compliance, warehouse layouts should be

designed to facilitate effective inventory control practices aligned with FEFO and FIFO principles.

Figure 1: Inventory control practices
Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

iv) Product Knowledge for Warehouse Officers

Additionally, the knowledge of warehouse officers regarding the supply chains of essential medicines was assessed accordingly at the MSD. Table 6 shows that 10 (20%) respondents enormously disagreed with the argument, 6 (12%) disagreed, 11 (22%) were neutral, 7 (14%) agreed, and 16 (32%) highly agreed. It was noticed that warehouse officers had sufficient knowledge of the products stored.

Table 6: Product knowledge for warehouse officers

Ranking category	Frequencies	Percent
Extremely Disagree	10	20
Disagree	6	12
Neutral	11	22
Agree	7	14
Extremely Agree	16	32
Total	50	100

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

v) Tendering Processes

Figure 2 presents the feedback from respondents about the tendering process. About 5 (10%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the argument, 6 (12%) disagreed, 3 (6%) were neutral, 11 (22%) agreed, and 25 (50%) strongly agreed. Overall, findings show that tendering processes compromised the supply chains of

essential medicines at MSD. The respondents reported that it is not surprising to see essential medicines expire before they are supplied to the respective health facilities. The tendering process can extend beyond 12 months, often surpassing the tender validity period, leading to a stock-out of essential medicines. Consequently, MSD loses substantial funds that would otherwise be channeled through its system, as health facilities resort to procuring from private suppliers.

Figure 2: Tendering processes of medicine
Source: Fieldwork Survey, 2022

vi) Automated system at MSD

The study analysed the feedback from the respondents on the automated system at MSD. Figure 3 presents the feedback from respondents on whether MSD has a computerised system to ensure the supply chains of essential medicines are maintained. About 8 (16%) of respondents strongly disagreed with the argument, 6 (12%) disagreed, 10 (20%) were neutral, 10 (20%) agreed, and 16 (32%) strongly agreed. MSD lacks an automated system to track dormant, obsolete, and slow-moving stock, relying on manual reviews using the internal inventory system that risk overlooking items until they near expiry.

vii) Operational challenge resulting in Expired medicine at MSD

The study analyzed feedback from respondents on the expiry issues in MSD due to poor inventory control. The findings in Table 7 showed that 7 (14%) strongly disagreed, 7 (14%) disagreed, 16 (32%) were neutral, 6 (12%) agreed, and 14 (28%)

strongly agreed. This implies that medicine expiries at MSD are not solely attributable to weaknesses in the inventory system but rather to factors such as prolonged procurement processes, where delays result in facilities sourcing from alternative suppliers, leaving MSD stock unrequested, delivery of items with short shelf life against TMDA importation guideline, and the absence of a clear accountability framework among employees responsible for stock management, all of which contribute to expiries

Figure 3: Automated system at MSD's zones
Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

Table 7: Expiries of medicine at MSD

Ranking category	Frequencies	Percent
Strongly Disagree	7	14
Disagree	7	14
Neutral	16	32
Agree	6	12
Extremely Agree	14	28
Total	50	100

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

viii) Local Pharmaceutical Manufacturers in the Country

The study analyzed feedback from respondents regarding local pharmaceutical manufacturers in the country. The results showed that 6 respondents (12%) were neutral, 13 (26%) agreed, and 31 (62%) strongly agreed as indicated in Table 8.

Table 8: Availability of local pharmaceutical manufacturers

Ranking category	Frequencies	Percent
Neutral	6	12
Agree	13	26
Extremely Agree	31	62
Total	50	100

Source: Fieldwork survey, 2022

Discussions

Funding Limitations

Results established in Table 4 showed that insufficient funding remains a major barrier to MSD operations, as a large number of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that inadequate funds undermine procurement. This finding is supported by the Controller and Auditor General report of 2019/20, which reported that only 52.5% of the approved budget for medicines procurement was disbursed, causing procurement delays (URT, 2021). The Ministry of Health (URT, 2021) also acknowledged that unpredictable funding weakens supply chains and threatens universal health coverage. Globally, Iyengar et al. (2021) found similar patterns, showing that financial gaps exacerbated supply disruptions during COVID-19 in low- and middle-income countries. Thus, this study's findings are consistent with both national and international literature, reinforcing the argument that funding predictability is critical for supply chain stability.

Procurement Regulations, Tendering Processes, and Inventory Management

Respondents in Figure 1 and Figure 2 reported that strict procurement regulations and lengthy tendering processes delay medicine availability, with over half agreeing or strongly agreeing. These results are supported by Wales et al. (2019), who found that rigid procurement frameworks in Tanzania often result in delays, and by Yadav (2020), who showed that complex tendering in developing countries creates uncertainty and stock-outs. The findings by Nieuwoudt (2020) also indicated that poor application of FIFO and FEFO in inventory management contributes to expiries and aligns with who linked to weak warehouse systems in sub-Saharan Africa to wastage. However, while literature generally points to warehouse-level

inefficiencies, this study adds nuance by showing that procurement rules and warehouse space constraints interact to deepen MSD's supply chain challenges. Thus, the findings are broadly supported by the literature but extend it to highlight systemic interconnections.

Technological Gaps and Monitoring Systems

Nearly half of the respondents in Figure 3 indicated that MSD lacks adequate automated systems to monitor stock and demand variations, which weakens forecasting. This finding is strongly supported by the Ministry of Health Quantification Guidelines (MOHCDGEC, 2018; reaffirmed URT, 2021), which cited poor data quality and inadequate digital systems as persistent obstacles. Globally, Zhou et al. (2021) and Wamba et al. (2022) demonstrated that digital platforms significantly improve supply chain responsiveness, a contrast to MSD's current situation. Therefore, this study confirms existing reports while adding evidence that weak automation not only affects forecasting but also leads to expired medicines due to delayed decision-making. The findings are therefore in line with the literature but show broader implications for shelf-life management.

Local Pharmaceutical Capacity and Persistent Stock-outs

Respondents as per Table 8, overwhelmingly agreed that limited local pharmaceutical production undermines medicine availability, leaving MSD dependent on imports. This finding is consistent with the Health Sector Strategic Plan V (URT, 2021–2026), which noted that only 25–30% of Tanzania's demand is met by local manufacturers. It is also supported by Makinde et al. (2021), who reported that African countries import over

70% of essential medicines, exposing systems to global price and supply shocks. Persistent stock-outs, highlighted by 88% of respondents, were similarly documented by Mponda et al. (2022), who linked shortages in Tanzanian facilities to poor accountability and forecasting. However, while previous studies largely emphasized facility-level shortages, this study extends the discussion to the MSD regional level, demonstrating how import dependency, combined with bottlenecks and delayed funding, generates systemic shortages. Thus, the findings are both supported by literature and contribute to a new angle by connecting supply chain weaknesses at national and zonal levels.

Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

This study concludes that the supply chain for essential health commodities in Tanzania, particularly within the Medical Stores Department (MSD), faces systemic challenges that undermine efficiency and equitable access. Inadequate and delayed funding, procurement processes and regulations, and inefficient tendering processes emerged as key barriers to timely medicine availability. Weak inventory management practices, including inadequate application of FEFO/FIFO due to warehouse layout design that do not support their effective implementation, coupled with limited automation and the absence of advanced digital forecasting tools, contribute to expiries, irregularities in demand management and persistent stock-outs. Furthermore, Tanzania's heavy reliance on imported pharmaceuticals, due to insufficient local manufacturing capacity, heightens vulnerability to global supply disruptions. While warehouse staff demonstrated sufficient product knowledge, systemic inefficiencies, particularly in procurement and resource allocation, continue to affect performance. These findings highlight the

urgent need for reforms in funding mechanisms, procurement flexibility, and advanced digital systems integration, alongside investment in local pharmaceutical production. Strengthening these areas is critical for building a resilient supply chain, reducing wastage, and ensuring reliable access to essential medicines nationwide.

Recommendations

To ensure the sustainability of the supply chain of essential medicines in Tanzania through the Medical Stores Department, the following are recommended:

- (i) The Government, through the Ministry of Finance in collaboration with the Ministry responsible for health, should ensure that funds for the procurement of essential health commodities are disbursed as per the projection and timely. This is because the performance of the MSD is constantly affected by fund availability, which in turn affects the implementation of MSD strategic plan 2021-2026 which is desired to improve stock availability at 90% as well as ensure financial sustainability
- (ii) Despite the reforms made in the Public Procurement Act and its regulations, the Government, through the Public Procurement Regulatory Authority (PPRA) in collaboration with the Ministry responsible for Health, should establish separate procurement documents to accommodate the special requirements of essential health commodities. These guiding documents should feature simplified procedures aimed at expediting the procurement of essential medicines to ensure continuous availability and timely delivery to health facilities.
- (iii) Further study should be conducted by other researchers to determine in detail how public procurement regulations that

require MSD to comply affect the patterns of stock availability. The findings of the survey will help to justify the importance of a separate guiding document specifically for the procurement of health commodities.

- (iv) The Government, through the Ministry of Industry and Trade in collaboration with the Ministry of Health, should support local pharmaceutical firms by empowering current manufacturing through tax breaks on raw material imports and subsidies on key utilities such as energy reducing production cost. Industrial pharmacists should be empowered by providing financial assistance to help them organize and develop production facilities at low interest rates. This strategy will boost the number of pharmaceutical industries and improve stock availability.
- (v) The Government through MSD should link its supply chain nodes with advanced technologies such as blockchain, Internet of things, Geospatial technology, Artificial Intelligence, robotics, open and crowd-based platforms as well as proximity technology to provide the best-automated systems in supply chain management including minimizing expiries and overstocked items. The advanced technology will facilitate demand variation management; quality of data submitted to procurement and traceability of logistic operations.

References

- Binyaruka, P., & Borghi, J. (2021). Improving health system efficiency in low-income countries: Insights from Tanzania. *Health Policy and Planning*, 36(3), 346–357. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czaa184>

- Controller and Auditor General (CAG). (2019). Annual general report of the Controller and Auditor General on the audit of the financial statements of the central government for the financial year 2018/19. National Audit Office of Tanzania. <https://www.nao.go.tz>
- Fox, E. R., & McLaughlin, M. M. (2022). US drug shortages compared to the World Health Organization's Model List of Essential Medicines for Children: A cross-sectional study. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*, 79(22), 2012–2018. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajhp/zxac236>
- Iyengar, K. P., Vaishya, R., & Bahl, S. (2020). Impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the supply chain in healthcare. *British Journal of Healthcare Management*, 26(6), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjhc.2020.0047>
- Khan, S. A. R., Yu, Z., Belhadi, A., & Mardani, A. (2020). Investigating the effects of renewable energy on international trade and supply chain performance. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 158, 104818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104818>
- Makinde, O. B., Jiyane, G. V., & Mugwisi, T. (2021). Information-seeking behaviour of science and technology researchers in Nigeria: A survey of the Federal Institute of Industrial Research Oshodi. *IFLA Journal*, 47(2), 259–271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0340035220931877>
- Mellahi, Kamel and Harris (2016), Response rates in business and management research : an overview of current practice and suggestions for future directions. *British Journal of Management*, 27 (2). pp. 426-437.
- Ministry of Health, Community Development, Gender, Elderly and Children (MoHCDGEC). (2018). Quantification guidelines for health commodities in Tanzania. Government of Tanzania. <https://www.moh.go.tz>
- Mponda, H., Mrema, J., & Ally, M. (2022). Factors influencing persistent stock-outs of essential medicines in Tanzanian health facilities: A systems approach. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice*, 15(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-022-00405-1>
- Mwangi, M., Achieng, L., & Njeru, R. (2022). Medicine stockouts and supply chain vulnerabilities in sub-Saharan Africa during COVID-19. *BMJ Global Health*, 7(5), e008482. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-008482>
- Nassani, A. A., Anser, M. K., Khan, M. A., & Abro, M. M. Q. (2021). Does COVID-19 pandemic disrupt sustainable supply chain process? Covering some new global facts. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(31), 42420–42436. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-14817-2>
- Ndomondo-Sigonda, M., Miot, J., Naidoo, S., Masota, N. E., Ng'andu, B., Ngum, N., & Walker, S. (2021). Harmonization of medical products regulation: A key factor for improving regulatory capacity in the East African Community. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 1881. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-10169-1>
- Nieuwoudt, M. (2020). Warehouse management practices and medicine availability in sub-Saharan Africa. *African Journal of Health Economics*, 9(1), 45–57.

- <https://doi.org/10.35202/AJHE.2020.9103>
- Singh, S., Kumar, R., Panchal, R., & Tiwari, M. K. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 1993–2008. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(7), <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2020.1792000>
- United Republic of Tanzania (URT), Ministry of Health. (2021). Health sector strategic plan V (HSSP V), July 2021–June 2026. Government of Tanzania. <https://www.moh.go.tz>
- Wales, J., Tobias, J., & Malangalila, E. (2019). Public procurement reforms and medicine availability in Tanzania: An evaluation of outcomes. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 32(5), 431–448. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPSM-09-2018-0194>
- Wamba, S. F., Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., & Akter, S. (2022). The performance effects of big data analytics and artificial intelligence in supply chain management. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 235, 108111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2021.108111>
- World Health Organization. (2019). WHO model list of essential medicines: on logistics systems and disruptions in food supply chain. *International Journal of Production Research*, 21st list, 2019. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-MHP-HPS-EML-2019.21>
- World Health Organization. (2021). Local production for access to medical products: Developing a framework to improve public health. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240010291>
- Yadav, P. (2020). Health product supply chains in developing countries: Diagnosis of the root causes of underperformance and an agenda for reform. *Health Systems & Reform*, 6(1), e1711823. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23288604.2019.1711823>
- Zhou, W., Huang, Y., & Wang, Y. (2021). Digital supply chain and resilience: Evidence from Asian pharmaceutical markets. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 26(6), 737–753. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SCM-09-2020-0508>